

Time Management & Organisation

Difficulty with time management and organisation

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Time Management & Organisation

Difficulty remembering the date, day or time

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Time Management & Organisation

Difficulty finishing tasks

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Time Management & Organisation

**Difficulty
sequencing and
completing
multi step
tasks**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Time Management & Organisation

Difficulty understanding time

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Time Management & Organisation

Difficulty planning for the future

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Time Management & Organisation

Difficulty avoiding
or managing
online distractions
such as Netflix or
social media

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Time Management & Organisation

Difficulties organising and managing files

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

